

Physiological and pathophysiological effects of L-tryptophan's metabolites on the brain and immunity – a challenge for drug development

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Abstract

The dysregulation of the kynurenine branch from tryptophan (TRP) metabolism can cause an imbalance between neuroprotective kynurenic acid and neurotoxic kynurenine metabolites in some psychiatric and neurodegenerative disorders. Therefore, the modulation of TRP metabolism may contribute to novel therapeutic strategies for several neuropsychiatric diseases. Targeting L-TRP-kynurenine pathway enzymes, particularly involving indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase-1, tryptophan 2,3-dioxygenase, kynurenine 3-monooxygenase, and kynurenine aminotransferase II, is a promising approach. The future development of potent selective inhibitors of these enzymes with a good safety profile would be a potential new avenue for the treatment of many diseases. The essential amino acid L-Tryptophan, together with its metabolites, plays a key role in diverse physiological and pathophysiological processes in the brain, especially in neurodegenerative and psychiatric disorders and autoimmunity. Also, TRP is a vital biochemical precursor for several functional neuroactive molecules, including serotonin and melatonin, which are of great importance for memory and learning, emotional regulation, circadian cycle, hunger, pain, etc. This article aims to underscore the links between tryptophan's metabolism and certain diseases of the central nervous system.

Keywords

tryptophan metabolism, serotonin, melatonin, kynurenic acid, major brain diseases

Introduction

L-Tryptophan is one of the essential mammalian α -amino acids, and its levels in humans are determined exclusively by dietary intake. Food poor in tryptophan (TRP) can induce nicotinamide deficiency, causing the metabolic disorder pellagra, which clinically manifests with dermatitis, diarrhea, and dementia.

The TRP molecule is made up of α -amino and α -carboxylic groups and a side chain indole group (a benzene ring fused to a pyrrole ring). This chemical structure gives

it its unique particularities as a polar molecule with prominent hydrophobic features (Palego et al. 2016). TRP, together with its metabolites, plays key roles in diverse physiological and pathophysiological processes and diseases like neurodegeneration, psychiatric disorders, cancer, and autoimmunity (Platten et al. 2019).

Moreover, the TRP-derived metabolites can serve as signaling molecules and neurotransmitters. As the only amino acid with an indole group, TRP is very important as a biochemical precursor for several functional neuroactive molecules, including serotonin (5-HT) and melatonin. The latter are of

utmost importance for plenty of physiological processes, such as the circadian cycle, memory and learning, emotional regulation, hunger, pain, gut motility, and secretion in the gastrointestinal tract (Roth et al. 2021; Klaessens et al. 2022).

General metabolism of tryptophan

Apart from its structural function in protein synthesis, there are three major metabolic pathways of the tryptophan metabolism—serotonin (neurotransmitter) pathway, kynurenine, and indole pathways, schematically represented in Fig. 1. Each of the TRP metabolic pathways is crucial in maintaining human homeostasis.

The kynurenine pathway is the one responsible for most of the catabolism of TRP (about 95%), which is not used for protein synthesis. It is also a metabolic route for the synthesis of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD). The first step in this pathway is to catalyze the indole ring cleavage at the C2, C3 bond of the TRP molecule, which is done by the tryptophan 2,3-dioxygenase (TDO) or the indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO). The resulting kynurenine from this stage is further metabolized to different molecules, among which are two inflammatory neuroactive mediators—quinolinic acid (QA) and kynurenic acid (KA). It follows that when TRP takes up the neurotransmitter pathway, it is important for the indole group to be intact, and when it takes on the kynurenine pathway, the first reaction is actually to open the pyrrole ring (Badawy 2017). A number of proinflammatory cytokines (particularly IFN- γ) stimulate the activity of IDO, whereas glucocorticoids induce the expression of TDO (Meng et al. 2014; Larkin et al. 2016). IDO1 is expressed in macrophages, microglia, dendritic cells, astrocytes, fibroblasts, and epithelial cells and is considered the key enzyme contributing to the formation of kynurenines in inflammatory diseases.

TRP plays the role of the only substrate necessary for the synthesis of serotonin (Hamon et al. 1981). This process occurs in two places—mainly in the distal portion of the gastrointestinal tract and in the central nervous system (CNS). The first step of metabolism is orchestrated by the tryptophan hydroxylase (TPH) (Fig. 2a), which has two isoforms—TPH1 and TPH2 located in the gut and the CNS, respectively. TPH converts tryptophan to L-5-

hydroxytryptophan (5-HTP), the precursor of serotonin, which is further converted to serotonin by the aromatic amino acid decarboxylase (AADC) (Fig. 2b). In the pineal gland the process continues—serotonin is acetylated by the arylalkylamine N-acetyltransferase (AANAT) to N-acetylserotonin (NAS), which is then methylated to melatonin via hydroxyindole-O- methyltransferase (HIOMT). Through this pathway the pyrrole ring stays whole (Boadle-Biber 1993; Borjigin et al. 2012; O'Mahony et al. 2015).

The metabolism of TRP in the gut biota goes through the indole pathway in which countless active indole derivatives are produced (e.g., indole, skatole, tryptamine, i3-pyruvate). Some of them show potency as ligands to the human aryl hydrocarbon receptors (AhR) (Vyhlídalová et al. 2020). The microbiome plays a key part in the tumor microenvironment (i.e., in colon cancer) and has an impact on the initiation, support, and response to the antineoplastic treatment (Wyatt and Greathouse 2021). This shows that the transformation of TRP in the microbiota through the indole pathway and the indole compounds themselves are altered in carcinogenesis (Yan et al. 2024). Indoxyl sulfate (IS) is a gut -derived metabolite from the indole pathway, which has the properties of a pro-inflammatory toxin and, together with a big part of the indole-based compounds, functions as a ligand to the AhRs (Dong et al. 2020).

It has long been believed that only exogenous molecules could be ligands, but recent studies have confirmed that a large number of endogenous substances can also be agonists of AhRs. These include not only aryl compounds found in the metabolism pathways of the gut microbiota but also photo-reactive catabolites of TRP, formed in the skin cells under ultraviolet (UV) exposure (Fritsche et al. 2007). Indeed, TRP is a chromophoric amino acid that undergoes photo-oxidation to 6-formylindolo[3,2-b]carbazole (FICZ), which acts as an endogenous ligand with high affinity to AhR (Rannug et al. 1987; Rannug et al. 2018). The AHR -activated cascade continues not only with the transcriptional induction of cytochrome P450 (CYP)1A1, but also with the internalization of the epidermal growth factor (EGF) receptor, activation with the EGFR's downstream target ERK1/2, and the following induction of cyclooxygenase (COX)- 2 (Degner et al. 2009). Because of that, the aryl hydrocarbon receptor's ligands may contribute to epigenetic modulation of inflammation and tumorigenesis (Wincent et al. 2009; Chaudhry et al. 2024).

Figure 1. Main tryptophan metabolites and pathways. KA—kynurenic acid, QA —quinolinic acid, NAD—nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide, XA—xanthurenic acid, IS—indoxyl sulfate.

Figure 2. The serotonin pathway of tryptophan metabolism.

Tryptophan metabolism in brain disorders

TRP deficiency impairs cognitive functions (Park et al. 1994). Moreover, the functional imbalance in the synthesis of biologically active products via TRP pathways causes various neuropsychiatric disorders (Davidson et al. 2022; Ye et al. 2024).

TRP metabolism in the brain by TDO and IDO in physiological conditions is much lower than its metabolism in the periphery (Dang et al. 2000). About 40% of KA in the brain is produced by the local TRP degradation.

Since the 1970s, a huge number of studies have shown that kynurenines can influence the function of the brain (Fathi et al. 2022a) and the neuroimmune system (Fujikawa et al. 2024). Different from several other kynurenine metabolites, KA and QA have a polar structure that does not allow them to cross the blood-brain barrier. Together with kynurenine metabolism in glial cells, the brain's uptake of these kynurenine metabolites is very important, as well as their production in the central nervous system (CNS). There is much evidence that the kynurenine metabolic pathway and one of its metabolites, specifically QA, play a significant role in numerous major neurological diseases (Schwarcz et al. 2012). Moreover, it has been well established that exactly the imbalance of the concentrations of kynurenine metabolites is tightly associated with the development of neurodegenerative disorders (Maddison and Giorgini 2015). Within the brain, the kynurenine catabolites act as ligands to the neuronal N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptors, which are post-synaptic calcium ion receptors. These receptors are glutamate-activated and are essential for the cognitive abilities (learning, memory, attention). Overactivation of NMDA receptors results in neuronal excitotoxicity. The KA, synthesized and released by astrocytes (Guillemin et al. 2000), plays a role as a potent receptor antagonist of the NMDA glycine binding site and is generally considered a neuroprotective factor. Vice versa, QA, which is primarily produced in the microglial cells, acts as a partial agonist to the NMDA receptors and exhibits neurotoxic properties (Guillemin et al. 2005a; Lugo-Huitrón et al. 2013).

Additionally, alterations in TRP metabolism may affect the development of anxiety and abnormal fear responses due to hyperfunction of kynurenine metabolism that contributes to activation of microglia in the hippocampus, amygdala, and prefrontal cortex (Klausing et al. 2020). The elevated levels of QA in the brain have detrimental effects on different aspects of memory and learning, including fear learning (Battaglia MR et al. 2023).

An impairment of the kynurenine pathway is also associated with other types of psychiatric pathology —major depressive disorder (MDD), bipolar disorder (BD), and schizophrenia (SZ). Wolfgang Marx et al. found in their meta-analysis of 101 studies that there is a reduction in the levels of TRP and kynurenine across MDD, BD, and SZ; decreased KA and QA ratio in the mood disorders (MDD, BD), while KA is not altered in SZ; decrease in the KA to kynurenine ratio in MDD and SZ, and a raise in the kynurenine to TRP ratio again in MDD and SZ (Marx et al. 2021). Alterations in the major route of TRP metabolism, the kynurenine pathway, have been observed in many neurodegenerative disorders. It was found that there are elevated levels of the excitotoxin QA and a change in the QA:KA ratio in serum and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) of patients with multiple sclerosis (Fathi et al. 2022b). Similarly, QA was measured to have increased in the hippocampus (Guillemin et al. 2005b) and in the peripheral mononuclear cells (Busse et al. 2018) of Alzheimer's disease patients. Therefore, these kynurenine metabolites are probably involved in the molecular mechanisms of Alzheimer's disease and could serve either as biomarkers or potential therapeutic targets for the disease (Liang et al. 2022). The hypothesis that elevated QA levels may have an important role in the striatal and cortical neurodegeneration of early-stage Huntington's disease was supported by many studies (Guidetti et al. 2006; Sapko et al. 2006). In addition, HPLC analysis convincingly demonstrated a strong reduction in KA concentrations in CSF and cerebral cortex in Huntington's disease (Beal et al. 1992), similarly to its decrease in CSF of Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease patients (Sorgdrager et al. 2019).

Furthermore, kynurenine as an endogenous ligand of AhR is constitutively produced by tumor cells in humans through TDO during cancer progression and inflammation. Binding to AhR, TDO-derived kynurenine enhances tumor survival

and suppresses anticancer immune response in an autocrine/paracrine manner. Such a signaling pathway (TDO–AhR) is found in primary brain tumors and is linked to tumor advancement and poor prognosis (Opitz et al. 2011; Guastella et al. 2018; Peyraud et al. 2022). Additionally, kynurenine also exhibits immunomodulating properties via AhR. Notably, L-Kynurenine interacts with the AhR, which stimulates the production of Tregs and up-regulates the programmed cell death-1 (PD-1) receptors in CD8+ T cells. This pathway is selectively active in IDO- and TDO- overexpressing tumors, and there is also an association between those types of tumors and therapeutic resistance to immune checkpoint inhibitors (Campeato et al. 2020; Charehjo et al. 2023.).

As a branch of TRP metabolism, the serotonin pathway is also important and has numerous effects that are not restricted to brain physiology. It was established that there is crosstalk between the serotonergic system and the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis. T. Mitsuma and T. Nogimori have found that the serotonergic system might have inhibitory effects on the TRH and TSH release in rats (Mitsuma and Nogimori 1983). In another study, acute L-TRP administration has decreased the TRH-induced TSH response, but without affecting the basal levels of thyroid hormones (Morley et al. 1980). Further, animal and clinical studies support the hypothesis that hypothyroid state reduces the central serotonin level and activity in the adult brain (Cleare et al. 1995; Upadhyaya and Agrawal 1993). Despite these observations, further investigation has to be done to clarify the connection between the serotonergic system and the thyroid axis.

Tryptophan metabolism as a pharmacological target in brain disorders

Targeting TRP metabolism gives new therapeutic opportunities and challenges for drug development in multiple brain disorders (Modoux et al. 2021). The kynurenine pathway as a terminal step of TRP degradation is implicated in the pathophysiology of neurological diseases. Therefore, any pharmacological modulation resulting in up-regulation of the KA levels in the brain may benefit these brain disorders (Pocivavsek et al. 2024). Indeed, high levels of KA can activate the synthesis of Nrf2 (Ferreira et al. 2018) and prevent ROS generation caused by QA (Ferreira et al. 2020). A recent review article brought together some of the evidence that supports a possible nutraceutical effect of KA given exogenously (Alves et al. 2024).

L-TRP-kynurenine pathway enzymes, particularly involving IDO1, kynurenine 3- monooxygenase (KMO), and kynurenine aminotransferase (KAT) II, are promising therapeutic targets for treatment of several neuropsychiatric disorders. Up-regulation of IDO, TDO, and KMO during inflammation and stress conditions is linked to an increased ratio of the neurotoxic to neuroprotective metabolites (Fujigaki et al. 2017). Intracerebroventricular application of lipopolysaccharide induces the brain IDO, resulting in a depressive-like

behavior in mice (Lawson et al. 2013). Therefore, IDO1 activation is related to the development of depression, and its inhibition could relieve the depressive symptoms, especially associated with other diseases, like diabetes and cancer (Qin et al. 2018). Pharmacological inhibition of IDO1 by its competitive inhibitor, the TRP analog 1-methyltryptophan, can be used to treat depressive-like behaviors. Also, a possible new mechanism of the old antidepressant desipramine is the ability to decrease IFN- γ -dependent IDO expression in the human and murine hippocampus, microglia, and astrocytes (Brooks et al. 2017). A recent study showed that coenzyme Q10 can change the balance between serotonin and kynurenine pathways through an inhibition of hippocampal IDO1, ameliorating the depressive state in rats (Abuezz et al. 2017). The development of potent IDO1 selective inhibitor(s) with a good safety profile would be a potential new avenue for treatment of depression.

In the brain, KMO is expressed mainly in microglia, whereas KAT II is predominantly expressed by astrocytes (Heyes et al. 1997). KMO inhibition decreases the synthesis of neurotoxic QA that directs the metabolism towards increased production of neuroprotective KA (Phillips et al. 2019). Several preclinical studies have demonstrated that KMO inhibition could serve as a promising therapeutic target in neurodegenerative disorders. The KMO inhibitor, JM6, can increase KA levels and reduce the extracellular glutamate in the brain. In a transgenic mouse model of Alzheimer's disease, JM6 is able to prevent anxiety-related behavior, spatial memory deficits, and synaptic loss, whereas in a model of Huntington's disease, it could decrease microglial activation and prevent synaptic loss (Zwilling et al. 2011). Similarly, in fly models of Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease, KMO suppression has improved locomotor performance and prolonged the life span, as well as alleviated neurodegeneration in Alzheimer's model flies (Breda et al. 2016).

KAT II is considered a main isoform, responsible for the majority of brain KA synthesis. KA elevation within the central nervous system has been observed in schizophrenic patients (Linderholm et al. 2012; Plitman et al. 2017). Studies have shown that KAT II inhibition and the consequent decrease of endogenous KA levels in the brain ameliorated cognitive performance in conditions relevant for schizophrenia (Kozak et al. 2014). N-acetylcysteine, a drug with pro-cognitive efficacy in humans, inhibits KAT II activity in brain tissue homogenates from rats and humans. With similar efficacy, N-acetylcysteine interfered with the de novo formation of KA in rat brains, and it showed competitive inhibition of recombinant human KAT II (Blanco-Ayala et al. 2020).

Conclusion

Finding new ways to modulate the metabolism of tryptophan could yield great benefits for the treatment of central nervous system disorders. The studies that have already been performed show promising results; however, more research is needed to fully grasp the possible treatments that could arise from this novel approach.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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